

Evaluation of Groundwater Quality and Its Suitability for Drinking and Agriculture Use of Nilanga Region Dist. Latur (Maharashtra State)

Miss. Bhagwatgeeta Prabhu Vairale

Research Student, Department of Zoology, Shivaji Mahavidyalaya Udgir, Dist. Latur Maharashtra state, India

Email: geet300993@gmail.com

Abstract

Nilanga is a town with a municipal council in Latur District in the Indian state of Maharashtra. It is also the headquarters for Nilanga taluka. Because of changing environmental condition due to globalization, population explosion and pollution. Maharashtra state (water supply section) assures the continuous supply of clean, safe drinking water for the public health protection. In this regard parameters to assess water quality are Colour, Taste and odour, TDS, PH, Temperature, Total Hardness, Electrical conductivity, Nitrates, Nitrites, Sulphate, Phosphate, Alkalinity, Salinity, Chloride, DO, Free Co₂, Carbonate and Heavy Metal Like Iron (Fe). Etc. of Tube well water, Tap water and Hand pump water sources of Nilanga region to conclude whether water is drinkable or not. The calculated values of these parameters were compared with Standard values set by the ICMR and BIS. The investigation is concluded by saying that the prevention of industrial and domestic sewage in ground water definitely help in controlling of water pollution. For the maintenance of good quality, suitability of drinking water which is in the form of domestic and agriculture.

Keywords: Nilanga city water sample, physico-chemical parameter, ICMR, BIS standard etc.

Introduction

Nilanga region is in Latur district in Maharashtra state India. The present location at Dist. Latur MH state of Area: 1,080Km², Population: 3, 25,255(2011), Latitude: 18°7'33.1500"N and Longitude: 76°45'3.4884"E. Latur district comprising 10 tahsils but only seven old tahsils i.e. Latur, Ausa, Renapur, Ahamadpur, Chakur, Udgir and Nilanga are considered for the study because of the non-availability of new tahsils data i.e. Devani, Jalkot and Shirur-Anantpal. Latur district is well inhabited and total population is 20, 80, 285 lived in 5 urban centers and 921 villages where as the density of population is 290.60 person per km². Water is important in each activity of life for living organism, population intensities and water viability. Many times not compatible Freshwater is essential for human health life and its quality is a matter of global concern. The surface water quality is very important and critical issue in many countries worldwide area.¹⁶

ii. Material And Method:

Selection of Sampling sites:-

The main concept of selecting sampling are based on the population and population density, areas of industrial or anthropogenic activities like, minerals and other toxic metals and effluents are realized directly in the catchment areas i.e. rivers, reservoirs also.

Sample Collections:-

All the drinking water is collected from the Tube well water, Tap water and Hand pump water from living areas. All the types of drinking water samples are open for public use like, houses, hotels, and schools, etc. All these samples were put in 1 liter polyethylene or plastic bottles. Before, using these bottles sanitized and deionized. After that all these bottles are named for their identification of samples, bottles are sealed and placed in a dark place at a normal temperature to away from any contamination and effects of temperature, light and other materials. Sample period of testing during the rain, summer and winter in 2021-2022.

Analytical Instruments:-One-Site Analysis

Laboratory Analysis:-

Physico-chemical parameters:-

The chemicals were prepared one day before by using the standard procedure given in American Public Health Organization (APHA)¹⁰ Methodology of water Analysis by M.S. Kodarkar and Practical ecology by K.S Rao. The physico-chemical parameters were studied by using the standard methods given in APHA, Methodology of water Analysis by M.S. Kodarkar¹⁷ and Practical ecology by K.S Rao. Physical parameters like Color odour and taste, Temperature, Turbidity, electrical conductivity and chemical parameters like pH, DO, Alkalinity,

Hardness, chloride and Salinity, Free CO₂, nitrate, nitrite, Sulphate, phosphate, and
Study Area: Map

heavy metal like iron were studied.

Figure: Shows the map of the Nilanga City and the areas of water sample in Nilanga city, Latur Distric, Maharashtra **Source:** google.com

Sr. No.	Sources	Locations
S-1	Tube well water	Anand Nagar
S-2	Tube well water	Bank Colony
S-3	Hand pump water	Laal Tekri
S-4	Hand pump water	Shivaji Nagar
S-5	Tap water	Balaji Nagar
S-6	Tube well water	Ghadge Nagar
S-7	Tube well water	Dapka
S-8	Tube well water	Dafedar Galli
S-9	Tube well water	Londhe Nagar

Table1. Show all collection of samples from different sources.
Results:

(All values except pH is in mg/l) Parameters	Standards	Recommended Agency	Unit Weight
pH	6.5-8.5	ICMR/BIS	0.2190
Total Alkalinity	120	ICMR	0.0155
Total Hardness	300	ICMR/BIS	0.0062
TDS	500	ICMR/BIS	0.0037
Calcium	75	ICMR/BIS	0.025
Magnesium	30	ICMR/BIS	0.062
Chloride	250	ICMR	0.0074
Nitrate	45	ICMR/BIS	0.0413
Sulphate	150	ICMR/BIS	0.0124
DO	5.0	ICMR/BIS	0.723

Table 2 Drinking water standards recommending agencies and unit weight.

Table 3 Shows Experimental Data of Physical and Chemical Parameters:

Table. 4 Experimental Data of Chemical Parameters Like: - Nitrate, Nitrite, Sulphate, Phosphate, Heavy Metal (Iron) (Values According to Spectrophotometer)

Sr. No.	Sources	Temperature (0c)	TDS (ppm)	Electric Conductivity (micromoh's-us/cm)	Chloride (mg/ltr)	DO (mg/ltr at NTP)	Free CO2	Carbonate	Phenolphthalein method	Methl orange method	Salinity	pH	Total
S-1	Tube well water	15	770	1.04	180.02	3.5	66	20	50	150	28.13	9.1	270
S-2	Tube well water	15	470	0.67	115.01	3.5	56	50	10	250	26.83	7.9	250
S-3	Hand pump water	20	760	1.14	170.02	3.71	50	200	150	150	31.83	8.7	370
S-4	Hand pump water	20	550	0.84	125.01	3.22	33	90	75	150	16.83	9.1	210
S-5	Tap water	40	310	0.45	80.01	5.13	30	40	165	216	21.83	9.3	150
S-6	Tube well water	15	340	0.5	61.5	4.9	26	90	53	255	37.59	9.2	210
S-7	Tube well water	15	240	0.35	76.51	5.1	40	50	150	1150	40.12	9.9	450
S-8	Tube well water	15	1250	1.93	56.5	6.4	30	160	100	1783	16.92	8.9	470
S-9	Tube well water	15	850	1.34	48.29	3.3	83	80	250	344	19.15	8.7	850

A

B

C

D

E

F

G

H

I

J

k

L

M

N

O

Graph: shows different parameter values
Conclusion and Suggestion:

1. In the present study after evaluation conclude about results of present water resource area of Nilanga city is highly contaminated with high values of TDS, hardness, pH, chloride, salinity, carbonate and alkalinity. The presence of high TDS in water it causes health problems. These abnormal values of parameter can be easily changed by testing the water time to time. Presence of high values of TDS, pH and hardness can be maintained by using the water softener and if there is also presence of high concentration of nitrate ion, then reverse osmosis process can be used.

2. Almost all the samples collected from different living and commercial areas of Nilanga region of Maharashtra state found to be beyond the recommended limit of ICMR and BIS standards. Heavy metal like iron value within the limits. So that, the quality of tap water, tube well water, w and hand pump water quality is poor and not totally safe for human consumption and for agricultural use. However, it also important that to evaluate other potential contaminants of water bodies like microbial and radiological substances and also includes human body fluids in that of Nilanga city.

3. After the study of physico-chemical parameters, here biological parameters also check in future study.

Acknowledgement:

The Author would like to especially thank to my Guide, Teachers and Department of zoology, Shivaji Mahavidyalaya Udgir for their support.

References:

1. **ICMR (1975)**, Manual of Standard of quality for drinking water supplies, Indian council of Medical Research spl., Rep. ser. No.44.
2. **WHO (1984)**, Guideline for water quality, Vol. recommendation World Health Organization, Geneva.
3. Physico-chemical Analysis of Ground Water in Latur Tehsil, Latur District (MH),Dharashive Sangmeshwar R1 and Agale Amar S2,Rajarshi Shahu Mahavidyalaya Latur (M.H.)- 413512
4. **Trivedi.R.K and Goel P.K. (1984)** book on chemical and biological methods for water pollution studies, Karad, Environmental Publication pp.1-251 M
5. **P.R.Trivedi And Gurdeep Raj.(1992)** Environmental water and soil analysis, first edition reprint 1995,1997,2005,2014,[ISBN 81-7158-261-3]. Practical work methodology of Physico-Chemical parameters Like electrical conductivity (P.N.77-81), Iron (P.N.172-175).
6. **Prof. K.S.Rao, (1993)**, Book of Practical Ecology, First Edition Practical work methodology of Physical ,Chemical parameters like free co₂,dissolved oxygen, salinity, hardness from page no.22-57, [ISBN: 81-7041-724-4].
7. **Biostatistics By P.Ramakrishanan, First Edition (1995)**, 1st Edition 2004, 3rd Edition 2007, 4th Edition 2017, [ISBN: 978-93-84826-04-8].Use for the analysis of statistical methods.
8. Bureau of Indian standard drinking water specification (BIS),(1997) New delhi,5,16
9. **Indian Association of Aquatic Biologists (IAAB) (2011)**, book on Methodology for Water Analysis (Physico-Chemical and Biological Parameters) By M.S.Kodarkar, A.D.Diwan, K.M. Kulkarni, Anuradha Ramesh.
10. **APHA (2005)**,Standard methods for the examination of water and waste water,21st edition, American Public Health Association, Washington DC, USA 1200
11. **Ashok Mohekar, Ravi Reddy, Mohan Babre (2005)**, A manual of fishery Sciences, Indrabai W.P.S.Nalini And Beebijohn, "Study on water quality in some selected areas of Tiruchirappalli city after the failure of North East monsoon". Poll.Res.24 (1)169-174.
12. **Wetzel R.G. Likens G.E (2006)** Limnological analysis. 3rdedition Sringer-Verelag, New York, 391.
13. **Kumbhar A.K & Et.al.(2009)**, "Study of Physico-chemical parameters of Ujjain reservoir in Solapur district, Maharashtra", Published in Journal of Ecology and Fisheries Vol.2 edited by Sakhare V.B. ISSN No 0974-6323 p 69-72.
14. GAANN-exp-9-Spectrophotometric determination of Phosphates of water Pdf.
15. **Hardness in drinking water (2011)**, background documents for development of WHO guidelines for drinking water quality WHO.
16. **Sehnaz sener, Erhan Sener,and Aysen Davrez, (2017)**. "Evaluation of water quality using water quality index (WQI) method and GIS in Aksu River (SW-Turkey)," Science of the Total Environment, vol. 584–585, pp. 131–144
17. **Indian Association of Aquatic Biologists (IAAB) (2011)**, book on Methodology for Water Analysis (Physico-Chemical and Biological Parameters) By M.S.Kodarkar, A.D.Diwan, K.M. Kulkarni, Anuradha Ramesh.